

Niyativāda vis-a-vis Doctrine of Karma

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Abstract

In today's world, it is confusing that one should follow *Niyativāda* or doctrine of karma. It is because wrong interpretation of spiritual books (*śāstras*). If one can't find the solution then he/she may lead to wrong conclusions and start believing that truth is very much complicated and beyond our capacity, but the fact is : truth is not at all complicated but right understanding from an enlightened being (*sadguru*) and Spiritual Gathering (*Satsaṅg*) is necessary.

People, who believe in *Niyativāda*, think that everything happens at the destined time and our endeavoring is of no use. There is strict chronological order and it is not possible to change or modify the order, while Doctrine of Karma preaches that only right endeavor is in our hand out of five elements for anything to materialize. So instead of waiting for time to come, one should do right endeavor (*puruṣārthā*) for desired result.

The purpose of this paper is to make utmost clarity of both the ideology. Both are right at their place but clear understanding of both the ideology is important. One should clear when to rely on *Niyativāda* and when to implement Karma theory (doctrine of karma). In order to present comprehensive understanding, author has studied both the ideology and intends to present right essence of *Niyativāda* and Doctrine of karma.

It is hoped that one should be able to develop a great deal of discrimination power to implement right ideology, at right time.

There are two ideologies having different concepts. Both have important roles to play in our lives but to pick the right one at the right time is paramount. These are *Niyativāda* and the Doctrine of karma. In this paper, we are going to discuss the truthfulness of both of these ideologies from different perspectives. Jainism defines the principle of *Anekāntavāda* or many-sidedness, which states that the ultimate truth or reality is complex, - and has multiple aspects. Let us first look at each ideology separately.

Niyativāda

People - who believe in this theory, think that everything happens at the destined time, and our endeavoring is of no use. There is strict chronological order and it is not possible to change or modify the order. They do not believe in right endeavor (*puruṣārtha*). Believer in this ideology become pessimistic and lethargic as they wait for the right time for destiny to blossom. People believing in this ideology, sometimes, blame God or karma for any undesirable occurrences, but they don't do anything to come out of this miserable state as according to them, endeavor brings no result.

Just believing in time and not doing the right endeavor is like assuming, - the crocodile as a wood plank that can take one across the river. Followers of this ideology behave very innocent but they are challenging their own concept! They are putting in effort in business and other material causes as they strongly believe that without earning, how could one sustain, that is, they believe in *puruṣārtha* in worldly things but when it comes to religion, they become lethargic and wait for the right time to come. This contradicts their belief of *Niyativāda*. If they truly believe in *Niyativāda*, they should follow this in any endeavor, in social or spiritual pursuits.

Jainism strictly believes in the doctrine of karma. According to Jainism, there are five factors necessary for something to happen. 1. Nature, 2. Right endeavor, 3. Instrumental factors, 4. Time, and 5. Destiny. These are also called the five *samavāy*. It says that nature, Instrumental factors, time and destiny are not in our hand; only right endeavor is. So instead of waiting for the right time to come, one should do right endeavor (*puruṣārtha*), - for the desired result to materialize. There is a beautiful combination of both the ideologies. One should do right endeavor (*puruṣārtha*), without thinking about destiny and as destiny unfolds, one needs to forget that he has done any *puruṣārtha* for that, as it was fixed as in “*Niyati (kramabaddha paryāy)*”

Jain Saint and self-realized Master, Shrimad Rajchandraji beautifully said, “*Strive real hard if you want to attain absolute truth; do not forsake the quest for truth in the name of destiny, fate etc.*” (Doshi, 2012, p. 231) Karma theory is pure science; one should not put their hands in fire, if he/she doesn't want to get burnt. Abstinence from indulging in activities that cause harm is also called endeavor. He also told that “*The seeker of truth would everywhere accept whatever is appropriate, and he would act accordingly in every situation.*”² It means, - that one should do one's share of effort, and not think or worry about the future or destiny, and when results come, either favorable or unfavorable, accept them with great reverence as it is not the result of your *puruṣārtha*; after all, the five *samavāy* would determine the result. Shrimadji also said that, “*Scriptures show the way of living and liberation but one true essence lies within the heart of the spiritual master, called sadguru.*”³ This is very relevant in today's life because we interpret, the meanings of scriptures according to our likes-dislikes, and not what the scriptures actually explained; but in

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1. *Rajgeeta*, (English translation with Commentary of *Shri Atmasiddhi Shstra*) – verse 130, Page 231
 2. *Rajgeeta*, (English translation with Commentary of *Shri Atmasiddhi Shstra*) – verse 8, Page 14
 3. *Shrimad Rajchandra*, Tenth Edition, letter 58 page 184.

the presence of the living master, there is no such scope of misinterpreting or delusion.

It is true that destiny plays a vital role in our life but to create destiny, one must do right endeavor. One cannot give all the power to time or destiny, as these are invisible things. Through right perception, right knowledge and right conduct, one should strive to materialize the dreams. One must take charge of one's destiny by doing right endeavor called *puruṣārtha*. One needs to understand which ideology is important at any given point of time, and it is understood with the help of the Enlightened being only because both are right but application of right thing at the right time is paramount; there are high chances that with our limited and impure intelligence, we will take it wrongly.

It is true that everything happens according to destiny, but here the question is - what decides destiny? If we think in detail, then it would come to surface that, - our endeavor (*puruṣārtha*) only creates our destiny. Only thing we need to understand is: past endeavor or present endeavor. Past endeavor creates our destiny for this birth and present endeavor creates destiny for our future lives and liberation too.

In history, there are many examples that support the doctrine of Karma, of which; - we will study two. The first example is of Swami Vivekanandji's life. Once a fortuneteller told Him that you can't earn fame as there is no line of fame on your palm, - He took a knife and immediately drew a line on His palm, and surely earned name and fame. The moral behind this story is, don't give too much importance to destiny because with a strong intention, we could write our destiny. The second example is of Mahatma Gandhiji; once He was told by Mr. Kripalani that there is no example in history where a war was won through Non-violence. He immediately replied, “If there is no

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1. *Inspiring Thoughts by Mahatma Gandhiji* : <https://quotes.thefamouspeople.com/mahatma-gandhi-55.php>

such history, then we will create history.”²⁴ He could have left the movement but instead, he fought with the weapon of non-violence only and brought freedom for India. Same thing applies to karma theory, - though destiny is fixed, we don't know what is there in our destiny, so through right endeavor, we need to unfold the mystery called destiny.

In every religion, religious gathering (*satsaṅg*) by an enlightened being has been applauded. We will understand the importance of religious gathering, - in perspective of *Niyativāda* and Doctrine of karma. As we know, every being behaves according to their instincts. Animals are behaving according to their instinct. Human beings have both the instincts, animal instinct and divine instinct. We have instinct of laziness, cowardliness, lust etc. and at the same time we have instincts of friendliness, steadfastness etc. It is very natural that we tend to follow sensual pleasures because it is easy, as we have practiced these through innumerable lives. *Satsaṅg* works on our belief system, as it nourishes our divine instinct and helps us eradicate our old bad habits. Therefore, it is called divine instinct building process. Here animal instinct means our rigidity to any one ideology; only *Satsaṅg* can eradicate our animal instinct and transform it into divine instinct called discrimination, love, passion and so on. The Enlighten being preaches that respect for all ideologies is good, but rigidity to any one ideology is the worst, as it doesn't allow you to think broad and reason for one remains in his/her own shell. One must transcend rigidity state of mind, as it is utmost necessary to perceive the knowledge of any principle, either *Niyativāda* or the doctrine of Karma.

It is very clear that religious gathering is one type of endeavor only but it is very necessary to uplift our lives. If we stick to *Niyativāda*, then changes are not possible, but through the lives of great spiritual beings, we see one thing very obvious that in the beginning or starting of their lives, they may have been full of animal instincts but as time went by, divine instincts replaced the animal instincts, and the

Enlightened Master emerged. Due to right endeavor, the thief ‘*vāliya*’ became the great sage ‘*vālmiki*’ through the *satsaṅg* of saint *Nārada* (*Nāradmuni*).

Shrimad Rajchandraji very beautifully explained the six philosophical tenets⁵ of the soul, in which He clearly mentioned that, soul is the doer and enjoyer of karma. We can justify both the ideologies by considering two stages, *Niyativāda* means witnessing mode, whatever the Omniscient Lord sees, it happens accordingly, - this is the ultimate form of *sādhanā*; witnessing alone and no doing; but one can reach that level only by right endeavor (*puruṣārtha*). We cannot neglect *puruṣārtha* in our spiritual practices. Indeed, our goal is not to remain occupied in endeavors, - our goal is witnessing mode alone, and in that witnessing mode, the concept of *-Niyativāda* manifests.

In other words, to be more precise, *Niyativāda* says that God/Godliness manifests by itself, there is no *purusharth* for manifestation. It is true but where does God manifest? Obviously it is not going to manifest in our turbulent *citta*. So it is very necessary to clean our *citta* for manifestation of God. -Cleaning or calming our *citta* again requires the right endeavor or *puruṣārtha*. Jainism says that it is very true that, whatever happens is according to the Omniscient. But having faith in *Dharma* or the Omniscient One again demands a lot of *puruṣārtha*.

It is tragic that we betray ourselves by following the scriptural principles at the wrong time. *Krama baddha paryāy* (*Niyativāda*) and *puruṣārtha*, both are deceiving when not applied at the right time. If you have a tendency to change the external circumstances, then it's better to do *puruṣārtha* to change the inner state, and when you reach a great spiritual state, - where you don't have the tendency to change others or circumstances for your benefit anymore, at that time *Niyativāda* would be the best thing to observe. If your belief system is so strong that you strictly adhere to the principle laid by *Shri Jina* that one substance, either living or non-living, cannot change or modify

another substance, then you are ready for the witnessing stage. At this stage you are just the observer, your peace and happiness don't come from outside or by changing substances outside, then you are ready for *Niyativāda* or *kramabaddha paryāy* but one should understand that having faith in *Niyativāda* requires a lot of *puruṣārtha*, right perception to correct your belief system. So instead of debating on which is true, one should understand that these are two stages of life. In the beginning, you need to do a lot of *puruṣārtha* and at the end, it is a sign of victory that you don't need to change anything for your happiness, and whatever comes according to destiny is acceptable and enjoyable for you. It is called firm understanding of *Niyativāda*. The Enlightened Ones are in the *Samādhi* state always, but what had made them to remain in *Samādhi* state always. The answer is - a lot of *puruṣārtha*. *Samādhi* state means just observe what is happening, that is, *Niyativāda*, but one important thing that has made them reach that state is tremendous spiritual endeavor.

One other aspect of using right philosophy at the right time (*Niyativāda* or *puruṣārtha*) is, by the example of our legs. We are free to lift one leg but after lifting one leg, we are bound to face the consequences. Like we are free to do karma, here *puruṣārtha*, either right or wrong, but once you do karma; you have to bear the fruits of that action. Here the understanding is, ***puruṣārtha* dictates *Niyativāda***.

According to *Niyativāda*, everything happens at the destined time and our endeavoring is of no use, which in turn is called fate, but here the question is, what decides our fate? Here two options would emerge.

1. God writes our fate.
2. We alone write our fate, but in the past.

We will deal with both the options in detail.

1. According to Jainism, Omnipotent God doesn't write our destiny, He remains in His pure state

2. This option is explained in Jainism as well both the theories, as in present, it is seen that everything is predetermined and events are piled up, coming to us without even consulting us!! This is fate. So we need to believe that every action would be determined by our past karmas, which is fate. *Niyativāda* itself promotes *puruṣārtha*, but it is not clearly seen because *puruṣārtha* has been done in our previous lives or in past and we shall reap fruits later (may be in this birth or next birth).

External events are not in our hands but the internal state is in our hand. External events are pre determined, and one not able to change or modify, but at the same time, not to have attachment with external circumstances - is *puruṣārtha* in itself. We are not identifying the preacher's real intention. Lord Mahavira showed karmic theory to the world, external events would occur as per the theory of karma (strict chronological order), and we need to be unaffected in any circumstances, either favorable or unfavorable, is *puruṣārtha*.

Jina's preaching is full of many view-points. Absolute view-point and relative or practical view point. It is true that everything happens at its stipulated time and with a strict chronological order. *Jina* also preached that while our karmas are in dormant state (*satta*), one can destroy majority of karmas by penance, which is kind of *puruṣārtha* only. So in any way, we cannot omit *puruṣārtha* in our spiritual practices, though it is true that everything is pre determined. In short, everything is destined but *puruṣārtha* is a key to unveil the destiny.

To sum up, a great saint and founder of Shrimad Rajchandra Mission, Pujya Gurudev Shree Rakeshbhai told that, consider our life like a book, in which God has written chapters called destiny, but in that book God left some pages blank, expecting us to fill these pages through right endeavor (*puruṣārtha*). It is great learning from both

1. Dr. U.K.Pungalia, *Philosophy and Spirituality of Shrimad Rajchandra*, Jaipur, Prakrit Bharati, 1st edition, 1996, Preface

the ideologies. Principles of Jainism propounded by Bhagwan Mahāvīra or principles of Buddhism laid by Gautam Buddha are equally applicable for determining *Niyativāda* or *puruṣārtha*, but one needs a spiritual mentor, who can unfold the mystery of Bhagwan's teachings.⁶ Only through right endeavor, we can reach the witnessing state which in turn is called Niyati. *puruṣārtha* would fuel *Niyativāda* and *Niyativāda* blossoms in the presence of *puruṣārtha*. It is like two sides of a coin, one cannot neglect any part, as both ideologies have their own standpoint.

(Most of the part of this paper is taken from Discourses of Pujya Gurudevshree Rakeshbhai)

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